

SAMPLED ANALOG LINKS

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Introduction

Demand for broadband radio-frequency (RF) analog signal distribution and processing is ever increasing for airborne, as well as terrestrial, applications. Analog optical links provide a number of desirable features for these applications including inherent bandwidth, immunity to electromagnetic interference, as well as reduced size weight and power. As the number of analog channels grows and link length increases new techniques that provide high-fidelity analog signal transmission are required. Sampled analog optical links – which employ a pulsed optical carrier in lieu of the conventional continuous-wave laser – offer several unique capabilities. In particular, these links offer time-division (as opposed to wavelength-division) multiplexing capability and immunity to stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) as a result of the broadband nature of the optical carrier. This talk will focus on sampled link operation and will discuss their use in long-haul analog photonic applications such as analog delay-line signal processing where SBS typically limits conventional link performance.

Sampled Link Operation

The sampled link geometry [1] is shown schematically in Figure 1 (a). The input RF signal modulates the output of a periodically pulsed optical source via a quadrature-biased Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM, $V_{\pi} \sim 2$ V). At the receiver end of the link, the modulated pulse train is detected with a high-speed photodiode (~ 20 GHz bandwidth). The RF signal is then recovered through low-pass filtering of the photodiode output. In this work, the pulsed source comprises a CW laser modulated by a low-biased MZM driven by a ~ 1 GHz step-recovery diode. The resulting optical pulse train consists of ~ 30 ps

Fig. 1 – (a) Sampled analog optical link. (b) Pulse trains measured at the photodiode.

pulses at a repetition-rate of 1-GHz. For operation in the first Nyquist band (no aliasing) the link analog bandwidth is, therefore, limited to < 500 MHz. To illustrate the pulse train, the current pulses as measured directly after the photodiode are shown in Fig. 1(b) for several average current levels. Note, as the pulse energy increases, high-field effects [2] lead to significant transit-time [3] broadening of the current pulse.

It has been shown that sampled link operation in the small-signal regime is described by *conventional* analog link theory [1]. The RF performance metrics (gain, noise figure, intercept points, dynamic range) are readily calculated from the average received photocurrent and modulator half-wave voltage. In the absence of significant photodiode nonlinearity, the link performance is identical to that of a conventional link operating at the same average photocurrent level. To illustrate the link performance, the measured RF gain and output third-order intercept point of the link (shown by the circles in both plots, at

a frequency of ~190 MHz) are shown vs. average photocurrent in Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b), respectively. There is excellent agreement between the calculated RF gain¹ (solid line) and the measured data up to ~20 mA where transit-time broadening begins to reduce the link gain [1]. Similarly, if we consider the link linearity as defined by the third-order intercept point (here, for intermodulation distortion²) we again see the dependence on average photocurrent is as predicted by conventional link theory (solid line). Here, however, high-field effects in the photodiode are seen to significantly impact link linearity at currents near ~10 mA. This illustrates a primary challenge in these links - as the average current increases, new techniques are required to mitigate photodiode nonlinearities (for example, photodiode arrays).

Fig. 2 - (a) RF gain and (b) output third-order intercept point of the link at ~190 MHz (from [1]).

Applications

While sampled links may be employed anywhere a conventional analog optical link is utilized, there are some unique capabilities enabled by the use of a broadband optical carrier. In particular, long haul applications could greatly benefit from the sampled architecture because the pulsed optical carrier helps to lessen the effects of stimulated Brillouin scattering. In this talk I will detail recent work at NRL in utilizing sampled links with tunable-bandwidth optical carriers (optical combs). By controlling the bandwidth (number of spectral features) in the comb, we have demonstrated the SBS threshold may be increased by over an order-of-magnitude (10 dB) in a 50-km fiber link. With further increases in comb bandwidth, we predict the SBS threshold may be increased by more than 20 dB using this technique.

References

- [1] J.D McKinney and K.J. Williams, "Sampled analog optical links," *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech.*, **57** no. 8, pp. 2093-2099, 2009.
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- [3] P.-L. Liu, K.J. Williams, M.Y. Frankel, and R.D. Esman, "Saturation characteristics of fast photodetectors," *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech.*, **47**, no. 7, 1297-1303, 1999.

¹ For matched photodiodes, the RF gain is given by $G = 1/4 \left(\pi I_{\text{avg}} / V_{\pi} \right)^2 R_o R_i$, where R_i and R_o are the input resistance of the MZM and the load resistance, respectively.

² The third-order output intercept point for intermodulation distortion and matched photodiodes is given by $OIP_3 = I_{\text{avg}}^2 R_o$.